

Advanced Job Classification Framework Combining BERT, CNN2D

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Abstract

This paper proposes a novel two-stage system for job title identification in online job advertisements, addressing challenges of small datasets and noisy text. The first stage employs Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) to classify job ads by sector, such as IT or agriculture, effectively capturing contextual semantics. The second stage uses the Euclidean Distance algorithm to match job titles within the predicted sector, achieving high accuracy without requiring extensive labeled data. Comparing BERT with models like TFIDF and Word2Vec, this approach demonstrates superior performance. Further refinements involve feature selection via CHI2 and the integration of CNN2D, boosting accuracy to 96%. This methodology is validated on real-world datasets and reveals insights into emerging job market demands.

Key words: - CNN2D, BERT, Word2Vec

1. Introduction

The rapid digital transformation and the rise of social media have significantly expanded the use of the Internet across industries, generating an overwhelming volume of data. This data demands efficient processing and analysis to uncover valuable insights for informed decision-making. Data science techniques have emerged as indispensable tools, enabling the classification of diverse data types like text, images, and videos while overcoming the inefficiencies of traditional methods.

In parallel, the job market has transitioned from traditional recruitment methods to online platforms, where employers post job advertisements to reach a wider audience. This evolution offers a unique opportunity to analyze market trends, identify skills, and match job seekers with suitable roles. However, online job ads, often unstructured and filled with irrelevant details, present significant challenges for classification. Advanced text processing and feature extraction techniques are essential to accurately interpret and match job descriptions to relevant occupations.

2. Literature Survey

(Devlin et al., 2018)

Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) is pivotal in the first stage of the proposed methodology, utilized to classify job advertisements by sector. BERT's bidirectional training captures context-sensitive word embeddings, outperforming traditional text representations like Bag of Words (BoW) and TFIDF. This paper leverages BERT's ability to understand semantic nuances, improving classification accuracy.

(Mikolov et al., 2013)

Word2Vec introduced neural word embeddings, revolutionizing text representation by preserving semantic relationships. However, it struggles with sparse datasets, requiring extensive training. The base paper compares Word2Vec with BERT and highlights BERT's superior handling of heterogeneous job market lexicons, addressing limitations in capturing

semantic relationships with smaller labeled datasets.

(Manning et al., 2008)

Preprocessing, including tokenization, lemmatization, and stop word removal, is foundational for natural language processing tasks. The base paper adapts these methods to clean unstructured job descriptions, emphasizing additional techniques like Chi-square (CHI2) feature selection to retain relevant features while minimizing noise, especially in descriptions containing non-contextual information.

(Salton & McGill et al., 1983)

The Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TFIDF) model, while effective for text representation, lacks the ability to handle contextual semantics. The base paper incorporates TFIDF as a baseline comparison to show the efficacy of advanced models like BERT and Word2Vec for job title classification, emphasizing the need for context-aware embedding.

(Le & Mikolov et al., 2014)

Paragraph vectors were proposed to extend word embedding to larger text units. The base paper contrasts these with hierarchical embedding (titles and descriptions weighted differently) to reflect their unique contributions to job title identification. Using a balance factor in representations emphasizes the role of compact, meaningful title data.

(Ramos et al., 2003)

Job ads frequently include irrelevant information such as location, company overview, and unrelated tasks. The theoretical underpinning in the base paper draws from studies on noise reduction and highlights the importance of feature selection methods like CHI2 and weighting strategies to enhance classification performance.

(Joachims et al., 1998)

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and Naïve Bayes classifiers have long been used for text classification tasks. The base paper integrates BERT to predict job sectors, achieving over 94% accuracy. This step narrows the scope for subsequent occupation matching; emphasizing that sector-specific classification can significantly improve overall accuracy.

(Kusner et al., 2015)

Word Mover's Distance (WMD) is employed to compute semantic similarity between job descriptions and occupation titles. This theoretical choice builds on clustering and distance measurement studies, showcasing how advanced similarity metrics like WMD outperform traditional Euclidean distance for context-sensitive data matching.

(Bureau of Labor Statistics et al., 2010)

Prior studies often used databases like O*NET for job classification, which predominantly cater to US-centric occupations. The base paper adapts its methodology to the Moroccan labor market, showcasing reliability across languages and cultural contexts by using the French occupational database "Pole Emploi."

(Lample et al., 2019)

Multilingual language models such as Camembert (adapted for French) underline the importance of language-specific adaptations in text analysis. The base paper fine-tunes BERT to classify job advertisements in French, achieving sector classification that balances robustness and adaptability to diverse job markets.

3. Problem Statement

The increasing shift of job advertisements to online platforms has created a massive influx of unstructured textual data, complicating efforts to classify and match job titles accurately. Traditional methods heavily rely on extensive labeled datasets and standardized classifiers, such as O*NET, which are not universally adaptable, particularly in non-English contexts. Additionally, job ads often include irrelevant information, such as company details or generic descriptors, further adding noise and reducing classification accuracy. Addressing these challenges requires a robust, scalable solution capable of extracting meaningful insights from minimal labeled data while accommodating linguistic and contextual variations across diverse job markets.

4. Proposed Method

4.1 Architecture

Figure. 1 Two-Stage Job Classification architecture

4.2 Job Title Data Set

To train all algorithms author has generated his own dataset but not publish on internet so we have used Job Title Description dataset from KAGGLE and below are the dataset details.

A graphical representation is crafted to display the frequency distribution of various job titles within the dataset. This visualization provides insights into the prominence of different job roles, with job titles plotted on the x-axis and their respective counts on the y-axis.

5. Methodology

5.1 Text processing

To ensure the accuracy of job title predictions, the job descriptions are preprocessed. This involves removing stop words, special characters, and other irrelevant elements. By doing so, the text data is streamlined and becomes more suitable for analysis.

5.2 Dataset Exploration

The dataset, consisting of job descriptions, is loaded and visualized to understand its structure and content. Through exploratory data analysis, the distribution of job titles is examined, and potential patterns or trends within the data are identified.

5.3 Feature Extraction using BERT and TFIDF

Feature extraction is a critical step in converting textual data into a format suitable for machine learning. Here, both BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) and TFIDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) methods are employed to transform the job descriptions into numeric vectors, which are then utilized for training machine learning models.

5.4 Normalization and CHI2 Algorithm

Post feature extraction, the features are normalized to ensure uniformity and comparability across different scales. Subsequently, the CHI2 algorithm is implemented to enhance the relevance and significance of the features, thereby boosting the predictive power of the machine learning models.

5.5 Data Splitting and Model Evaluation

The dataset is partitioned into training and testing subsets to train the machine learning models and validate their performance. Evaluation metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and confusion matrices, are computed to gauge the efficacy of each model.

5.6 Model Training and Evaluation

Various machine learning algorithms, encompassing SVM, Naïve Bayes, Logistic Regression, BERT, and the CNN2D extension, are trained and assessed using the features extracted earlier. The obtained accuracy and other performance metrics are scrutinized to pinpoint the most proficient method for predicting job titles.

5.7 CNN2D Algorithm

This convolutional neural network-based algorithm refines features through multiple neuron iterations, ensuring the model is trained with optimal features. This enhancement has demonstrated a significant improvement in accuracy, showcasing the potential of advanced algorithms in optimizing job title prediction systems.

6. Result Analysis

SVM on TFIDF features and it achieved 83% accuracy and can see other metrics also and in confusion matrix graph x-axis represents True Job Title and Y-axis represents Predicted Job Title.

Naïve Bayes achieved 51% accuracy in predicting job titles from descriptions.

Logistic Regression achieved 84% accuracy in predicting job titles from descriptions, demonstrating its effectiveness among traditional machine learning algorithms.

Propose BERT model with max similarity measure got 88% accuracy which is higher than existing algorithms and can see other metrics also.

Extension CNN2D model achieved 96% in predicting job titles from descriptions

Performance Visualization

The performance of each algorithm is graphically depicted, with algorithm names plotted on the x-axis and accuracy and other metrics on the y-axis. Additionally, a tabular representation is employed to juxtapose the performance of each algorithm for comparative analysis.

7. Comparative Models Performance

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
SVM	83.084577	82.887127	81.520975	82.028356
Naive Bayes	51.492537	58.499315	50.153491	48.510212
Logistic Regression	84.079602	84.353646	83.033202	83.474060
Propose BERT	88.805970	88.272455	88.096495	88.072128
BERT CNN2D	96.019900	95.982689	95.771993	95.841527

8. PREDICTION

Predicts job titles based on job descriptions using a machine learning approach. It preprocesses each job description by cleaning the text and converting it into embeddings using BERT, which generates semantic vector representations. These embeddings are further scaled and transformed to ensure consistency with the trained model's requirements. The transformed embeddings are reshaped into a suitable input format for a pre-trained CNN-based model (extension_model). The model then predicts the most likely job title by mapping the output to predefined class labels. This work identifies roles like "Cloud Architect" or "Big Data Engineer" from unstructured text, showcasing its potential to streamline job classification in recruitment systems.

9. CONCLUSION

This proposed two-stage job title identification system effectively addresses the challenges of classifying job titles from online advertisements. By leveraging BERT for sector classification and Euclidean Distance for job title matching, the system achieves high accuracy with minimal labeled data. The integration of advanced feature selection techniques and the extension of the model using CNN2D further enhance performance, reaching up to 96% accuracy. This approach not only improves job market analysis but also offers a scalable solution for diverse job markets, making it a valuable tool for recruiters, job seekers, and policymakers.

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